

MOOC EO Open Data Science - ESA AO/1-11113/22/I-DT

Deliverable FR – Final Report

This document summarizes the progress that has been made from the beginning of the project on 01.10.2022 up to the project final meeting at 13.03.2024.

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Contents

Abstract.....	1
General Progress.....	2
WP100 Concept	4
WP110 Workshop	4
WP120 Concept Development.....	5
WP200 Production	6
WP210 Video Production.....	6
WP220 Video Post-Production	7
WP230 Exercise Content.....	8
WP240 Exercise User Experience.....	9
WP250 Lecture Content.....	10
WP300 Development	11
WP310 Course Deployment.....	11
WP320 Course Hosting and Administration	12
WP400 Outreach and Dissemination.....	13
WP500 Project Management.....	14
Important Links	14

Abstract

The Massive Open Online Course '**Cubes & Clouds - Cloud Native Open Data Sciences for Earth Observation**' teaches the concepts of data cubes, cloud platforms and open science in the context of earth observation.

Target Group: It targets Earth Science students and researchers who want to increase their technical capabilities onto the newest standards in EO computing, as well as Data Scientists who want to dive into the world of EO and apply their technical background to a new field. Before starting, prerequisites are a general knowledge of EO and python programming.

Content: The course explains the concepts of data cubes, EO cloud platforms and open science by applying them to a typical EO workflow from data discovery, data processing up to sharing the results in an open and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) way. An engaging mixture of videos, animated content, lectures, hands-on exercises and quizzes transmits the content.

Learning Objectives: After finishing the participant will understand the theoretical concepts of cloud native EO processing and have gained practical experience by conducting an end-to-end EO workflow. The participant will be capable of independently using cloud platforms to approach EO related research questions and be confident in how to share research by adhering to the concepts of open science.

Figure 1: Elevator Pitch Presentation of the MOOC Cubes and Clouds

General Progress

The general progress of the project is in line with the planned progress up to the second payment milestone, the final review meeting. All due deliverables are produced and delivered to ESA. The progress across the specific Work Packages is summarized in the following sections. The overall time line and progress can be tracked in Figure 1 and Figure 2. The status of the deliverables is depicted in Table 1. A prolongation of 6 months has been granted to the project in order to complete complex tasks, like establishing single sign on between EOCollege and EOX Hub.

Figure 2: Gantt Chart tracking the status of the project. The end of the project has been shifted by 6 months.

Figure 3: Project Time vs. Project Progress per Work Package

Figure 4: Work Breakdown Structure with initial time line (a prolongation of 6 months has been granted) and the logical connection of the work packages.

Doc ID	Description	Date	Type	WP	Partner	Notes	DOI
D1	Review Document	KO + 1M	Report	100	Eberle	Delivered	10.5281/zenodo.10833996
D2	Requirement Document	KO + 2M	Report	100	EOX	Delivered	10.5281/zenodo.10834583
D3	MOOC Content	KO + 3/6M	Electronic data package	200	EURAC	Delivered (GitHub , Zenodo , EOCollege)	10.5281/zenodo.10513914
D4	Course Report	CCN MTR	Report	300/400	EOS	Annotated Usage Statistics at MTR of CCN	-
D5	MOOC Usage Analytics Report	CCN MTR	Report	300	EOS	Access Link to EOCollege Dashboard	-
AB	Abstract / Executive Summary	KO + 12M	Report	500	EURAC	Delivered	10.5281/zenodo.10838724
FR	Final Report	KO + 12M	Report	500	EURAC	Delivered	10.5281/zenodo.10839572
CCD	Contract Closure Documentation	KO + 12M	Report	500	EURAC	After CCN closes	-

Table 1: List of deliverables

WP100 Concept

WP110 Workshop

- Motivation:
 - Get to know each other, jointly decide on the focus of the course and align expectations.
- Activity:
 - 2 Day Workshop in Bolzano
 - Topic delineation and choice
 - Gain insights into the theory of e-learning
- Output:
 - Outline for WP 120 Concept Development

Figure 5: Brainstorming of expectations during the Concept Workshop.

Figure 6: Outline of the course contents.

WP120 Concept Development

- Motivation:
 - Create a full outline of the course, create the red thread to follow, collect state of the art and existing material to build upon. The outcomes (D1 – Review Document and D2 – Requirements Document) serve as reference for WP200 where the content is created.
- Output:
 - D1 Review Document [10.5281/zenodo.10833996](https://zenodo.org/record/10833996)
 - D2 Requirements Document [10.5281/zenodo.10834583](https://zenodo.org/record/10834583)

Figure 7: Excerpt from D1 – Review Document.

WP200 Production

WP210 Video Production

- Motivation: Use videos to shine a light on specific details within the topic by including international experts of the field.
- Activity:
 - Text and video template to ensure uniformity have been created
 - Texts have been produced in collaboration with international experts
 - Videos have been produced in a professional setting with a professional speaker
- Output:
 - 14 videos of about 3 minutes each

Figure 8: Picture taken while shooting the videos with a professional speaker.

OpenEO in action

Here’s an example of openEO in action. In the initial openEO project we compared multiple cloud platforms using the openEO API. We sent the same processing graph to each cloud platform. In this example we calculate the Enhanced Vegetation Index using Sentinel 2 data and then take the minimum EVI value over time. As you see the same set of commands produced results on each backend without changing the code. And the results are identical!

Estimated Time

Note: This is a Textbox. The Table and Text in this Textbox are not counted towards number of words.

This table estimates the time of your video. Only **enter the number of chapters**, according to your headings above. To calculate the estimated time automatically select the whole table (or click [ctrl+a](#) while in this textbox) and hit F9.

WORDS	CHAPTERS	WPM	SPEAKING TIME (MIN)	TOTAL TIME (MIN)
362	3	120	3.02	3.6

Aim your Total Time of the video to be 2.5 to 3 minutes.

Figure 9: Example of a video script automatically calculating the length of the video.

WP220 Video Post-Production

- Motivation:
 - Bring the videos into a common shape, length and style, so that the learning experience is completely integrated and participants feel the coherence within the course.
- Activity:
 - Images, Icons and Logos used in the videos have been harmonized to a unified look
 - A trailer has been created as an animation movie explaining what the course is about
 - Animated Content, Reworking of Images (Numbers)
- Output:
 - 14 unified videos of about three minutes each and one trailer (embedded in the lectures, hosted on the [EOCollege youtube channel](#))

Figure 10: Screenshot of the videos produced for Cubes and Clouds hosted on the EOCollege youtube channel.

Figure 11: Example of a video embedded in EOCollege Cubes and Clouds.

WP230 Exercise Content

- Motivation:
 - Create hands-on exercises that lead the participants to working on cloud platforms
- Activity:
 - The exercises follow a transition from easy to difficult
 - The exercises are openly available on GitHub and open for collaboration
 - The final exercise is a Community Mapping Project, where every participant uploads their fair results to a web map (STAC Browser)
- Output:
 - [Nine exercises as python notebooks](#) (to be found with the lectures)

Figure 12: Screenshot of the coding environment created for Cubes and Clouds on EOX Hub.

Figure 13: The community mapping STAC Browser “Cubes and Clouds – Snow Cover”

WP240 Exercise User Experience

- **Motivation:**
 - Create an integrated user experience starting from EOCollege. The topic of cloud computing calls for external services to be integrated (e.g. EOx jupyter hub, CDSE, etc.). The transition has to be as smooth as possible for the participants.
- **Activity:**
 - EOCollege serves as the Single Entry Point for the course (Single Sign-On, SSO)
 - JupyterHub with predefined environment
 - Direct link from lecture to notebook via button
 - Data and exercise transfer directly from GitHub (one pull updates everything)
 - Community map integrated with results obtained at EOx Hub
- **Output :**
 - Single Sign-on established between EOCollege and EOx Hub
 - [Registration video for CDSE](#)
 - Buttons in EOCollege that link directly to the exercises on EOx Hub
 - Python environment for the exercises
 - [Community map \(STAC Browser\)](#) integrated with results obtained at EOx Hub

Figure 14: Part of the Single Sign On Procedure.

Exercise

Now we have covered the most important topics of our use case in theory. Let's move on to produce some results! ⚠ The applied workflow is a simple approach used for educational reasons to learn how to use EO cloud platforms.

Exercise

Figure 15: Button that connects EOCollege lectures with the exercises on EOx Hub.

WP250 Lecture Content

- Motivation: Create appealing and engaging lecture content for the topics of cloud native EO and open science in EO.
- Activity :
 - Create content for the lectures
 - Create animated content for the lectures (e.g. interactive drag and drop games)
 - Content reviewed by experts in the respective fields
 - Lectures openly available for collaboration following open science principles (DOI, etc.)
 - Lectures available on GitHub, Zenodo, EOCollege
- Output:
 - [12 lectures](#)
 - 16 animated content widgets newly created and embedded into the lectures. Access to the [raw H5P widgets via EOCollege Creation Hub](#), only accessible if granted access by EOCollege.
 - D3 MOOC Content (Electronic Data Package) [10.5281/zenodo.10513914](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10513914)

FAIR Expert!

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H-P

Figure 16: Example of an animated content interactive drag and drop game.

WP300 Development

WP310 Course Deployment

- **Motivation:**
 - The course material should be available in an dedicated e-learning platform - EOCollege containing quizzes, exercises, animated content, diplomas, embedding all content, feedback and statistics.
- **Activity:**
 - Transfer material from GitHub to EOCollege
 - Internal Testing: Four internal project collaborators tested the course and left feedback, which has been implemented.
 - External Testing: More than ten external participants tested the course and left feedback, which has been implemented.
- **Output:**
 - [Tested course on EOCollege integrating all material](#)

Figure 17: Cubes and Clouds landing page on EOCollege.

Figure 18: Example of a quiz in Cubes and Clouds on EOCollege.

WP400 Outreach and Dissemination

- Motivation:
 - Advertise the course so that the maximum number of relevant participants subscribe.
- Activity:
 - Conferences:
 - 2023: FOSS4G, IGARSS, BiDS, → Links DOIs
 - 2024: EGU, FOSS4G EU, Open Geo Hack Summer School
 - Socials:
 - X/Twitter and Instagram ESA + Reposts
 - LinkedIn Eurac EO + Reposts
 - Homepages/Blogs: Every Partners News
 - Networks: Every Partner reaches out to their networks (e.g. pyladies, open earth monitor cyberinfrastructure)
 - Universities: Inform universities via mail and suggest to include the MOOC into their CV
- Output:
 - [Promotion Material](#) (project internal)
 - [Detailed Promotion Plan](#) (project internal)
 - [LinkedIn post](#), [X](#), [ESA Blog](#) (the promotion is still ongoing while writing this report)
- Publications:
 - IGARSS 2023: P. J. Zellner et al., "MOOC EOODS - Massive Open Online Course for Earth Observation and Open Data Science: A Course to Educate the Next Generation PF EO Researchers in Data Cubes, Cloud Platforms, and Open Science," IGARSS 2023 - 2023 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium, Pasadena, CA, USA, 2023, pp. 1200-1202, doi: [10.1109/IGARSS52108.2023.10282262](https://doi.org/10.1109/IGARSS52108.2023.10282262)
 - FOSS4G 2023: Zellner, P., et al, "MOOC EOODS - Massive Open Online Course for earth observation and open data science: a course to educate the next generation of EO researchers in data cubes, cloud platforms and open science," 2023. url: <https://talks.osgeo.org/foss4g-2023/talk/RFCAYS/>
 - BiDS 2023: Zellner, P., et al, "MOOC EOODS - Massive Open Online Course for earth observation and open data science: a course to educate the next generation of EO researchers in data cubes, cloud platforms and open science,". Open & Reproducible workflows in Earth Observation (OREO) – Big Data From Space 2023, Vienna, Austria.
 - EGU 2024: Zellner, P. J., Balogun, R. O., Eckhardt, R., Hodam, H., Dolezalova, T., Meißl, S., Eberle, J., Claus, M., Callegari, M., Jacob, A., and Anghelea, A.: Cubes & Clouds – A Massive Open Online Course for Cloud Native Open Data Sciences in Earth Observation , EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-21733, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-21733>, 2024.

Figure 21: First promotion post on LinkedIn.

WP500 Project Management

- Motivation:
 - Manage the project so that all partners can work ideally together, that there is a clear communication pathway and tasks can be assigned and progress can be tracked.
- Activity:
 - Communication via Teams Channel and GitHub Repository
 - Meetings held on a bi-weekly basis
 - Progress see General Progress
 - A Contract Change Notice has been designed to prolong the project in order to integrate more topics and diversify the processing
- Output:
 - Teams Channel (for internal communication and task assignment)
 - [GitHub Repository](#) (for external communication and issues tracking)
 - Contract Change Notice for prolonging the project

Figure 22: Screenshot from the Cubes and Clouds Team Channel used for internal communication and task planning.

Important Links

- Cubes and Clouds Course on EOCollege: <https://eo-college.org/courses/cubes-and-clouds/>
- Cubes and Clouds GitHub Repository: <https://github.com/EO-College/cubes-and-clouds>
- Cubes and Clouds Zenodo Community: https://zenodo.org/communities/cubes_and_clouds/
- Cubes and Clouds STAC Browser: <https://esa.pages.eox.at/cubes-and-clouds-catalog/browser/#/>